

Digital Forensics on Solid State Drive (SSD) with TRIM Feature Enabled and Deep Freeze Configuration Using Static Forensic Methods and ACPO Framework

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Abstract— For digital forensic examiners, data files are important because it can be used as digital evidence. The integrity of digital evidence must be accessible, displayed, and guaranteed its integrity so that it can be accounted for in court. One of the places to store data files is Solid State Drive (SSD). Facts and problems were found on the SSD because there are three technology updates including TRIM feature, garbage background collection and wear leveling which can eliminate data files that have been deleted automatically. Several tools can be installed on SSD such as deep freeze. Deep freeze function is to protect the computer from unwanted changes. If the data files is saved after the deep freeze is activated, then the computer is shut down and turned on again, the data files on the SSD will be lost (not saved). The purpose of this research was to determine the probability of success in recovering data and extracting data based on number of files and the percentage on the SSD with deep freeze configuration. In this research will use static forensic methods and the research stage, scenario testing will be performed 3 times by following the ACPO framework. Of the examination and analysis already performed, only 2 of 4 tools have succeeded for recovering and extracting for partial data, namely Autopsy and Photorec. The percentage of success rate for recovery and extract of data has decreased from the first test until third test. If the computer already deep freeze configured is shutdown or restarted more than once, the less likely files that can be recovered. That is still an obstacle for forensic examiners, where the results of digital evidence cannot be recovered and extract as a whole.

Keywords- digital forensics; ssd; trim; deep freeze; acpo framework; examination; analysis; recovery; extract; digital Evidence

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional hard disks are slowly becoming a thing of the past because new data storage technology continues to demand a lighter, faster, and more reliable alternative to Solid state drive (SSD). SSD have penetrated the market in an effort to meet this demand (1). SSD which has a more efficient form and has a technology update that makes accessibility faster which has a

way of working background without being noticed by the user. Because the way SSD works does not always ensure that the data is deleted, but sometimes SSD can clean up data by itself. Here illustrates the changes in digital forensic activities, where digital forensic investigators have new challenges related to data recovery in SSD to provide digital data evidence and also play a role in how to preserve digital evidence that is potentially lost, destroyed or considered invalid as evidence (2) (3).

SSD is equipped with 3 update technologies, including the TRIM feature, Garbage background collection (GBC), and Wear leveling, which can eliminate data files that have been deleted, they provide significant problems for forensic investigators (4) (5). As a result, the number of investigations requiring digital forensic expertise is likely to increase in the future (6). TRIM feature, Garbage Background Collection and wear leveling on the SSD function to clean files that have been permanently deleted from that sector in a few minutes (7). Digital criminals have the potential to destroy digital evidence on SSD, because three technology updates including TRIM feature, garbage background collection and wear leveling which can eliminate data files that have been deleted without special instructions from a computer or desktop (8) (9) (10). On SSD, several tools can be installed such as deep freeze. Deep freeze function is to protect the computer from unwanted changes. If the data files is saved after the deep freeze is activated, then the computer is shut down and turned on again, the data files on the SSD will be lost (not saved), this makes the challenge of a digital forensic investigator (11).

Digital forensics consists of two methods, namely static forensics and live forensics. Static forensics uses conventional procedures and approaches where electronic evidence is processed in a bit-by-bit image to conducting the forensic process. The forensic process runs on a system that is not on or running (off). While, live forensic uses analysis procedures where electronic evidence can be analyzed directly in the condition of digital devices in living conditions, but does not get effective results (12). Digital forensic examinations must use

forensic tools, where forensic tools are used by forensic investigators to searching for digital evidence by analyzing and extracting data of digital evidence (13).

Based on the above problems and the challenge faced is how to obtain digital evidence like files on SSD with TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration that could potentially be used for digital crimes. In this research we proposed using the static forensic methods to the process copy of SSD (imaging of SSD) using 2 tools namely FTK Imager and DD. The research stages following the ACPO framework and analysis of digital forensics using 4 tools namely FTK, Autopsy, OSForensics, and Photorec. In this research, we made the following contributions and novelty:

- The imaging process of SSD with TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration using 2 forensic tools, namely FTK Imager and DD which can be used as references for future research.
- The scenario testing was performed 3 times to obtain how many files can be recovered on SSD with TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration, so that it can be used as references for future research that has tested more than once.
- The results of the implementation in this research, digital evidence as some files was found. Using 2 examination tools namely Autopsy and Photorec successfully recovered files and extracted files from 3 test scenarios that have been done

II. RELATED WORKS

Related works are investigates an issue with the SSD that could automatically destroy digital forensic evidence. The research method used is conducting 3 experiments, formatting the SSD and analyzing the SSD (TRIM feature enabled) using PC Inspection as the examination tools. The result is no data were found from the 3 experiments that had been carried out. TRIM feature, garbage background collection, and wear leveling can complicate the digital forensic process (14).

On the SSD there are 3 update features such as wear leveling, TRIM, and garbage background collection to become a new challenge in digital forensic investigations that can destroy digital evidence on an SSD without any or instructions to do from a desktop or computer. The research method used is conducting experiments, comparing HDD and SSD with the tests carried out, copying data to HDD and SSD then formatting partitions on the HDD and SSD. Tools used by the Forensic Toolkit (FTK) for the examination process. The results of the implementation on HDD, we could find 1099 files out of 1964 original files or could identify 60% of the files that were deleted. But, the results of the implementation on SSD, could only identify 760 files out of 1964 original files in SSD or could identify less than 40% of the files that were deleted. Based on this experiment and the results is proved to be a new challenge in digital forensic investigations for find of the digital evidence (15).

Issue related to searching for digital evidence on hard drive that has been frozen. Digital forensic analysis with static forensic

methods. Conducting investigations on file documents (.doc & .xls), file pictures (.jpg & .png), internet history and open recent. As a comparison, the analysis process using 4 tools namely autopsy, winhex, photorec and foremost for the examination process. The results digital forensics analysis of frozen hard drive, Winhex v15.9 can analysis of digital evidence better than Autopsy v4.0, Photorec v6.14, and Foremost v6.14. Winhex v15.9 could find of file documents (.doc & .xls), file pictures (.jpg & .png), internet history and open recent. Foremost only could find of file pictures (.jpg & .png). But, Autopsy v4.0 and Photorec v6.14 could not find the overall file documents (.doc & .xls), file pictures (.jpg & .png), internet history and open recent (11).

Issue related to searching for digital evidence on HDD and SSD. Discussing the differences in forensic analysis on HDD and SSD by comparing the two forensic tools used, namely FTK and Autopsy. On the HDD, the results of the forensic analysis were successfully carried out without a hitch. In contrast to SSD, there were obstacles with the TRIM feature that could destroy digital evidence so that it experienced difficulties in forensic analysis because some data could not be recovered (16).

This research examine the problems by forensic examiners in performing data recovery on SSD due to the TRIM feature which can clean data in seconds. Experiments have been carried out on SSD with the TRIM feature disabled almost all data can be recovered. But with the TRIM feature enabled feature only 27% of data can be recovered (17).

The difference between this research and the previous research is the imaging process of SSD using 2 forensic tools, namely FTK Imager and DD. The result of file image from FTK Imager will conducting analysis using Autopsy, FTK and OSForensics. But, the result of file image from DD will conducting analysis using Photorec. The analysis process will following ACPO framework with 3 test scenarios. This research was conducted to find the best solution for the problems or the digital crime found on SSD with TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration.

III. THEORY

A. Digital Forensics

Forensic examinations will report when a document is being created, when it was first discovered in the system, when it was last edited, when it was last modified, and last saved (18). The integrity of any original evidence is fundamental to a forensic examination. Preserving the integrity of digital evidence is vitally important as changing just one bit among perhaps gigabits of data, will irrevocably alter that data and cast doubt on any evidence extracted (19). The process of extracting, conserving, analyzing, and documenting forensic investigations can be improved by a framework that supports investigators during work, linking evidence gathered by various forensic tools (20).

B. Association of Chief Police Officers (ACPO)

In the digital crime handling of evidence of a problem or case, a guideline is needed which aims to make all processes starting from the search, collection, processing and presentation

of the evidence findings can be accepted in court. The methods used in the ACPO document: Plan (Planning), Capture (Record or Documentation), Analyze and Present (Results Presentation) (21). The existing four ACPO principles is the guidance and framework which can be used by practitioners digital forensics (22).

C. TRIM

TRIM is the method of data removal in the SSD (23). The TRIM function deletes the data blocks that are marked as 'deleted'. When the OS has deleted a file, it can issue a TRIM command to the SSD as a "not used" marker. This allows the SSD to physically rearrange the location associated with the file (19). The researchers concluded that the retention of data deleted from the SSD could at least be maintained or recovered. Researchers show that on SSD that enable TRIM, using an Operating System (OS) that supports TRIM, that in most cases no data can be recovered (17). TRIM is still provide significant problems for forensic investigators (24).

D. Deep Freeze

Deep freeze functions to maintain computer configuration. Every change is intentional or unintentional when rebooting. This concept is called reboot-to-restore, where each reboot returns the computer to the desired configuration (25). This is in line with what Deep Freeze's software development company said on its website deepfreeze.com.au, software to freeze drives can reduce computer maintenance costs by 63%, so as to save on maintenance costs for offices, agencies and internet cafes in Indonesia to adopt this software (11).

E. Static Forensics

Static forensic is the process imaging (copy data byte by byte) done while the computer is turned off. In static forensics, all the needs for forensic analysis are obtained using various types of external devices such as USB. Static forensic tool searches the storage media for discovering digital evidence (12). Static Forensics focuses on examining duplicate copies of disks to retrieve data contained in them, such as deleted files, web browsing history, network connections, user login history, and others (11).

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research framework is the reference for determining the stages to be conducted in the research. Then proceed with a discussion of the proposed methods to obtain solutions to the research problem.

A. Proposed Methods

Figure 1. Stages of Research with ACPO framework

In Figure 1, the propose methods in this paper by following the ACPO framework. Step 1 is PLAN, preparing scenario on SSD (TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration). On simulation computer, we will provide the files on flash disk for copying to SSD (TRIM feature enabled and deep freeze configuration). Step 2 is CAPTURE, we will conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data. Using the static forensic methods to the process of copy (imaging of SSD). The imaging process of SSD using 2 forensic tools, namely FTK Imager and DD. Step 3 is ANALYSE, we will analysis of digital forensics using 4 tools namely FTK, Autopsy, OSForensics, and Photorec to get result as comparison. After analysis using 4 tools, we will conducting examination for verification and validation of digital evidence using hashing technique. Step 4 is PRESENT, reporting of the implementation result on digital evidence that has found.

B. The process of Copy (Imaging of SSD)

In this research, propose methods for imaging of SSD using static forensic methods. The process of copy (imaging of SSD) will conducting when the computer is turn off. The imaging process of SSD using 2 forensic tools, namely FTK Imager and DD. Step the process of copy (imaging of SSD) can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Static Forensic Methods for Imaging of SSD

C. Digital Forensics Analysis

After the process imaging of SSD, the next step is digital forensic analysis. The step is digital forensic analysis can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Step of Digital Forensic Analysis

The step of digital forensics analysis begins, the result image file of SSD using FTK Imager will conducting examination and analysis using FTK, Autopsy and OSForensics. The result image file of SSD using DD will conducting examination and analysis using Photorec. The next step is examination and searching of digital evidence from analysis using 4 tools examination. If digital evidence is found, next conducting validation digital evidence using hashing technique. If digital evidence not found, it will proceed to the next stage. The last step is reporting and presentation of result analysis digital evidence.

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULT

In the research, implementation of the test scenario will be performed 3 times. First testing of scenario can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. First Testing of Scenario

The first step in the first test scenario is turn on the computer simulation that contain SSD of 180 GB. The second step is conducting check the TRIM feature enabled. The third step is to install deep freeze. The step four is to copy data as document files, pictures files, audio files and videos files from flashdisk of 16 GB has been prepared to SSD of 180 GB. The step five is turn

off the simulation computer. The step six is to plug SSD of 180 GB to examiner computer that contain HDD of 1 TB. The step seven is conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data. The step eight is conducting process imaging of SSD using 2 tools namely FTK Imager and DD. The step nine is conducting to analysis and examination from the result file image using 4 tools namely FTK, Autopsy, OSForensics and Photorec along conducting validation digital evidence that has been found using hashing technique. The last step is reporting and presentation digital evidence that was successfully recovered and extracted.

Figure 5. Second and Third Testing of Scenario

In Figure 5, on the second and third test scenarios, there is no need to check the TRIM feature and deep freeze configuration because it has been done in the first test scenario. So, the first step on the second and third test scenarios is turn on the computer simulation that contain SSD of 180 GB. The second step is to copy data as document files, pictures files, audio files and videos files from flashdisk of 16 GB has been prepared to SSD of 180 GB. The third step is turn off the simulation computer. The step four is to plug SSD of 180 GB to examiner computer that contain HDD of 1 TB. The step five is conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data. The step six is conducting process imaging of SSD using 2 tools namely FTK Imager and DD. The step seven is conducting to analysis and examination from the result file image using 4 tools namely FTK, Autopsy, OSForensics and Photorec along conducting validation digital evidence that has been found using hashing technique. The last step is reporting and presentation digital evidence that was successfully recovered and extracted.

A. Implementation of The First Test Scenario

1) Checking the TRIM Feature

In the simulation computer, conducting check the TRIM feature enabled using instruction “*fsutil behavior query DisableDeleteNotify*” on CMD, can be seen in Figure 6.

```
Administrator: Command Prompt
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.17134.1610]
(c) 2018 Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.
C:\Windows\system32>fsutil behavior query DisableDeleteNotify
NTFS DisableDeleteNotify = 0 (Disabled)
```

Figure 6. TRIM Feature Enabled

If “*NTFS DisableDeleteNotify = 0*” its mean the TRIM feature is enabled and if “*NTFS DisableDeleteNotify = 1*” its mean the TRIM feature is disabled. On SSD, the TRIM feature is actually enabled by default before any changes from the administrator on the computer.

2) Deep Freeze Configuration

In Figure 7, deep freeze has been installed on the simulation computer. There is only one partition on the SSD (C Drive) that has been deep freeze configured.

Figure 7. Deep Freeze Configuration

3) Copy Files

In the simulation computer, performing the copying of data as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files from flashdisk of 16 GB has been prepared to SSD of 180 GB. In Figure 8, there are 51 files with a total size of 228 MB that have been copied to the SSD.

Figure 8. Collection of Files on the First Test Scenario

4) Write Blocking

Before conducting the process imaging of SSD, it must conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data, can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Write Blocking Configuration

5) Imaging of SSD

After conducting the write blocking, the next process on the examiner computer is to create an image file on the SSD using 2 tools namely FTK Imager and DD. The process of imaging using FTK Imager on SSD of 180 GB takes 39 minutes and 27 seconds, can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Result of Imaging Process Using FTK Imager

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 11, looks the same as the original file structure and result of image file structure.

Figure 11. Original File (Left), Result of Image File (Right)

The process of imaging using DD on SSD of 180 GB takes 14 hours and 46 minutes, can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Result of Imaging Process Using DD

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 13, the original file structure same as result of the image file structure.

Figure 13. Original File (Left) and Result of Image File (Right)

6) Digital Forensic Analysis

After the process imaging using FTK Imager and DD, the next process is analysis of the file image using 4 tools examination. The first tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using FTK. Results of the analysis using FTK, no files were found from the 51 files that were copied in the first test scenario, this is due to license limitations so that FTK could only accommodate a maximum of 5000 file items that can be analyzed, can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Analysis Processs Using FTK

The second tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using Autopsy.

Figure 15. Analysis Processs Using Autopsy

In Figure 15, there are 32761 deleted file that consists of multiple file extensions. The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 51 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 51 original files with 32761 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques. There are 25 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file (hashing techniques) can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Extracted Files Using Autopsy

The third tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using OSForensics. There are 4540 deleted files were found. In contrast to the autopsy, OSForensics not found 51 files that have been copied in the first test scenario, can be seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Analysis Processs Using OSForensics

The fourth tool, result of imaging file from DD will to analysis using Photorec. In Figure 18, there are found 14023 files has been recovered and extracted.

Figure 18. Analysis Processs Using Photorec

The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 51 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 51 original files with 14023 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques. There are 44 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file (hashing techniques) can be seen in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Extracted Files Using Photorec

The results of the first scenario test using FTK, Autopsy, OSForensic and Photorec can be seen in Table 1.

TABLE I. RESULTS OF FILE EXTRACTION IN FIRST TEST SCENARIO

Extension Files	Total Files	Total of Extracted Files			
		FTK	Autopsy	OSForensics	Photorec
Doc. Files					
.doc	9	0	9	0	12
.ppt	2	0	1	0	1
.pdf	14	0	8	0	14
Pict. Files					
.jpg	3	0	3	0	4
.png	1	0	1	0	1
.gif	1	0	1	0	1
Video Files					
.mp4	5	0	0	0	2
.3gp	4	0	0	0	0
Audio Files					
.mp3	12	0	2	0	9
TOTAL	51	0	25	0	44
Result of Percentage	100%	0%	49%	0%	86%

B. Implementation of The Second Test Scenario

1) Copy Files

In the simulation computer, performing the copying of data as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files from flashdisk of 16 GB has been prepared to SSD of 180 GB. In Figure 20, there are 140 files with a total size of 282 MB that have been copied to the SSD.

Figure 20. Collection of Files on the First Test Scenario

2) Write Blocking

Before conducting the process imaging of SSD, it must conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data, can be seen in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Write Blocking Configuration

3) Imaging of SSD

The process of imaging using FTK Imager on SSD of 180 GB takes 1 hours and 6 minutes, can be seen in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Result of Imaging Process Using FTK Imager

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 23, looks the same as the original file structure and result of image file structure.

Figure 23. Original File (Left) and Result of Image File (Right)

The process of imaging using DD on SSD of 180 GB takes 12 hours and 40 minutes, can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Result of Imaging Process Using DD

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 25, looks the same as the original file structure and result of image file structure.

Figure 25. Original File (Left) and Result of Image File (Right)

4) Digital Forensic Analysis

The first tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using FTK. Results of the analysis using FTK, no files were found from the 140 files that were copied in the first test scenario, can be seen in Figure 26.

Figure 26. Analysis Processs Using FTK

The second tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using Autopsy.

Figure 27. Analysis Processs Using Autopsy

In the Figure 27, there are 6353 deleted file that consists of multiple file extensions. The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 140 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 140 original files with 6353 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques.

In Figure 28, there are 54 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file

(hashing techniques). There are 4 of 54 files from the first test scenario.

Figure 28. Extracted Files Using Autopsy

The third tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using OSForensics. There are 35 deleted files were found. In contrast to the autopsy, OSForensics not found 140 files that have been copied in the first test scenario, can be seen in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Analysis Process Using OSForensics

The fourth tool, result of imaging file from DD will to analysis using Photorec. In Figure 30, there are found 15439 files has been recovered and extracted.

Figure 30. Analysis Processs Using Photorec

The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 140 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 140 original files with 15439 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques.

In Figure 31, there are 57 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file (hashing techniques). There are 3 of 57 files from the first test scenario.

Figure 31. Extracted Files Using Photorec

The results of the first scenario test using FTK, Autopsy, OSForensic and Photorec can be seen in Table 2.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF FILE EXTRACTION IN SECOND TEST SCENARIO

Extension Files	Total Files	Total of Extracted Files			
		FTK	Autopsy	OSForensics	Photorec
Doc. Files					
.doc	20	0	3	0	3
.ppt	10	0	0	0	2
.pdf	20	0	19	0	20
.xls	15	0	4	0	4
Pict. Files					
.jpg	20	0	1	0	2
.png	20	0	20	0	19

.gif	10	0	6	0	6
Video Files					
.mp4	10	0	1	0	1
.3gp	5	0	0	0	0
Audio Files					
.mp3	10	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	140	0	54	0	57
Result of Percentage	100%	0%	39%	0%	41%

C. Implementation of The Third Test Scenario

1) Copy Files

In the simulation computer, performing the copying of data as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files from flashdisk of 16 GB has been prepared to SSD of 180 GB. In Figure 32, there are 200 files with a total size of 341 MB that have been copied to the SSD.

Figure 32. Collection of Files on the Third Test Scenario

2) Write Blocking

Before conducting the process imaging of SSD, it must conducting write blocking on examiner computer to prevent the exchange of data, can be seen in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Write Blocking Configuration

3) Imaging of SSD

The process of imaging using FTK Imager on SSD of 180 GB takes 54 minutes and 49 second, can be seen in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Result of Imaging Process Using FTK Imager

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 35, looks the same as the original file structure and result of image file structure.

Figure 35. Original File (Left) and Result of Image File (Right)

The process of imaging using DD on SSD of 180 GB takes 13 hours and 21 minutes, can be seen in Figure 36.

Figure 36. Result of Imaging Process Using DD

The next step is conducting validation and verification the original file with result of image file. In Figure 37, looks the same as the original file structure and result of image file structure.

Figure 37. Original File (Left) and Result of Image File (Right)

4) Digital Forensic Analysis

The first tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using FTK. Results of the analysis using FTK, no files were found from the 200 files that were copied in the first test scenario, can be seen in Figure 38.

Figure 38. Analysis Process Using FTK

The second tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using Autopsy, can be seen in Figure 39.

Figure 39. Analysis Process Using Autopsy

There are 6320 deleted file that consists of multiple file extensions. The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 200 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 200 original files with 6353 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques. In Figure 40, there are 61 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file (hashing techniques). There are 2 of 61 files from the first test scenario.

Figure 40. Extracted Files Using Autopsy

The third tools, result of imaging file from FTK Imager will to analysis using OSForensics. There are 35 deleted files were found. In contrast to the autopsy, OSForensics not found 200 files that have been copied in the first test scenario, can be seen in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Analysis Process Using OSForensics

The fourth tool, result of imaging file from DD will to analysis using Photorec. In Figure 42, there are found 6162 files has been recovered and extracted.

Figure 42. Analysis Process Using Photorec

The next step is to extract all deleted files and search for the 200 files that have been copied in the first test scenario. From the results of the examination by matching 200 original files with 6162 deleted files by validating and verifying using hashing techniques. In Figure 43, there are 76 files as document files, pictures files, audio files and video files has successfully validated and verified by matching the hash value of each file (hashing techniques). There are 2 of 76 files from the first test scenario.

Figure 43. Extracted Files Using Photorec

The results of the third scenario test using FTK, Autopsy, OSForensics and Photorec can be seen in Table 3.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF FILE EXTRACTION IN THIRD TEST SCENARIO

Extension Files	Total Files	Total of Extracted Files			
		FTK	Autopsy	OSForensics	Photorec
Doc. Files					
.doc	20	0	13	0	17
.ppt	20	0	0	0	9
.pdf	20	0	12	0	13
.xls	20	0	3	0	3
Pict.Files					
.jpg	20	0	6	0	6
.png	20	0	14	0	14
.gif	20	0	8	0	9
Video Files					
.mp4	20	0	0	0	0
.3gp	20	0	5	0	5
Audio Files					
.mp3	20	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	200	0	61	0	76
Result of Percentage	100%	0%	30%	0%	38%

VI. CONCLUSION

Result of digital forensic analysis on SSD with deep freeze configuration using 4 tools, only 2 tools that can recover and extract files namely Photorec and Autopsy. The time required for analysis using Photorec is faster than Autopsy. The analysis using Photorec need 1-2 hours. But, using Autopsy takes 6-10 hours. Of three test scenarios that have been done, the percentage of success rate for recovery and extract of data has decreased from the first test until third test. It can be concluded if the computer already deep freeze configured is shutdown or restarted more than once, the less likely the files to be recovered or the less the percentage that can be obtained. Digital forensics analysis on SSD with deep freeze configuration is still an

obstacle for forensic examiners in conducting digital forensic analysis, where the results of digital evidence cannot be recovered and extracted as a whole.

In the first test scenario using Photorec there are 44 files from 51 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 86%. However, using Autopsy there are 25 out of 51 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 49%, can be seen in Figure 44 and Figure 45.

Figure 44. The Results of Extraction Files on First Test Scenario

Figure 45. The Results of Extraction Files on First Test Scenario

In the second test scenario using Photorec there are 57 files from 140 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 41%. However, using Autopsy there are 54 out of 140 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 39%, can be seen in Figure 46 and Figure 47.

Figure 46. The Results of Extraction Files on Second Test Scenario

Figure 47. The Results of Percentage on the Second Test Scenario

In the third test scenario using Photorec there are 76 files from 200 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 38%. However, using Autopsy there are 61 out of 200 files that can be recovered and extracted with a percentage of 30%, can be seen in Figure 48 and Figure 49.

Figure 48. The Results of Extraction Files on Third Test Scenario

Figure 49. The Results of Percentage on the Third Test Scenario

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Neyaz, N. Shashidhar, and U. Karabiyik, "Forensic Analysis of Wear Leveling on Solid-State Media", Sam Houston State University Huntsville (USA), 2018, pp. 1706-1710.
- [2] F. Geier, "The differences between SSD and HDD technology regarding forensic investigations", Linnaeus University (Sweden), 2015, pp. 1-67.
- [3] P. Bednar, V. Katos, "SSD: New Challenges for Digital Forensics", Lund University (Sweden), October, 2011, pp. 1-8.
- [4] A. Nisbet, R. Jacob, "TRIM, Wear Levelling and Garbage Collection on Solid State Drives: A Prediction Model for Forensic Investigators", Auckland University of Technology (New Zealand), 2019, pp. 419-426.
- [5] A. Aldaej, M. G. Ahamad, and M. Y. Uddin, "Solid State Drive Data Recovery In Open Source Environment", Prince Sattam bin Abdulaziz University (Saudi Arabia), 2017, pp. 228-231.
- [6] B. Van Houdt, "Performance of garbage collection algorithms for flash-based solid state drives with hot/cold data", University of Antwerp (Belgium), 2013, pp. 692-703.
- [7] B. R. Joshi, R. Hubbard, "Forensics Analysis of Solid State Drive (SSD)", University of Nebraska Omaha (USA), May, 2016, pp. 1-67.
- [8] Y. Gubanov, O. Afonin, "Why SSD Drives Destroy Court Evidence, and What Can Be Done About It", Belkasoft Ltd, 2013, pp. 1-10.
- [9] G. Bell, R. Boddington, "Solid State Drives: The Beginning of the End for Current Practice in Digital Forensic Recovery?", Murdoch University (Australia), December 2010, pp. 1-20.
- [10] J. Vieyra, M. Scanlon, "Solid State Drive Forensics: Where Do We Stand?", University College Dublin (Ireland), March, 2018, pp. 1-16.
- [11] F. Albanna, I. Riadi, "Forensic Analysis of Frozen Hard Drive Using Static Forensics Method", Islamic University of Indonesia (Indonesia), January, 2017, pp. 173-178.
- [12] M. Rafique, & M. Khan, "Exploring Static and Live Digital Forensics: Methods, Practices and Tools". International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, 2013.

- [13] Z. E. Rasjid, B. Soewito, G. Witjaksono, E. Abdurachman, "A review of collisions in cryptographic hash function used in digital forensic tools", Bina Nusantara University (Indonesia), October, 2017, pp. 381-392.
- [14] Z. Shah, A. N. Mahmood, J. Slay, "Forensic Potentials of Solid State Drives", University of New South Wales Canberra (Australia), September, 2015, pp. 113-126.
- [15] S. S. R. Marupudi, "Solid State Drive: New Challenge for Forensic Investigation", St. Cloud State University (Minnesota), August, 2017, pp. 1-100.
- [16] Y. R. Kambalapalli, "Different Forensic Tools on a Single SSD and HDD, Their Differences and Drawbacks", St. Cloud State University (Minnesota), May, 2018, pp. 1-88.
- [17] C. King, T. Vidas, "Empirical analysis of solid state disk data retention when used with contemporary operating systems", Carnegie Mellon University (USA), 2018, pp. S111-S117.
- [18] B. B. Meshram, D. N. Patil, "Digital Forensic Analysis of Hard Disk for Evidence Collection", Veermata Jijabai Technological Institute (India), January 2018, pp. 100-110.
- [19] P. Tobin, N. Le-Khac, M. Kechadi, "A Lightweight Software Write-blocker for Virtual Machine Forensics", University College Dublin (Ireland), 2016, pp. 730-735.
- [20] G. Fenu, F. Solinas, "Computer Forensics Investigation An Approach To Evidence In Cyberspace", University of Cagliari (Italy), 2017, pp. 77-88.
- [21] ACPO, "ACPO Good Practice Guide for Digital Evidence", Association Of Chief Police Officers, 2012.
- [22] G. Horsman, "ACPO principles for digital evidence: Time for an update?", Teesside University (England), February, 2020, pp. 100076.
- [23] N. Reddy, "Solid State Device (SSD) Forensics", Osmania University (India), 2019, pp. 379-400.
- [24] F. Yohannes, "SSD Digital Forensics Construction", The Polytechnic University of Milan (Italy), 2011, pp. 1-59.
- [25] F. Corporation, "Deep Freeze Standard User Guide", Faronics Corporation, 2010.